

Checklist organization & software process in use

- Is there a basic understanding of the company and its organizational structure? Are project-specific details known?
- What software process is being used?
- Is there a basic understanding of the model being used, including any customized adaptations?
- Is there a basic understanding of role definitions, their tasks, and competencies?
- Which teams are being observed and interviewed?
- Are the project conditions of the relevant teams known?
- Are all (agile) meetings time-boxed?

Checklist Daily Scrum

- What is the purpose of the meeting?
- Is there a basic understanding of meeting rules?
- Does every team member participate (speaks) during the Daily Scrum?
- How is the status communicated?
- What is the frequency of the meeting?
- Does the meeting always take place at the same time and location?
- Are employees from other locations involved? If so, how?
- Are stakeholders allowed to participate in the meeting?
- Is the sprint board used in the meeting (visual representation of work items, user stories, impediments, etc.)?

Checklist Retrospective

- What is the purpose of the meeting?
- Is there a basic understanding of meeting rules?
- Is a specific model used for the retrospective? (e.g., Starfish Model)
- Are stakeholders allowed to participate in the meeting?
- How is the result documented?

Checklist Sprint Review

- What is the purpose of the meeting?
- Is there a basic understanding of meeting rules?
- Who presents the results? Who decides on the acceptance of the results?
- Are stakeholders allowed to participate in the meeting?
- How are decisions (acceptance Yes/No) recorded?

Checkliste Sprint Planning

- What is the purpose of the meeting?
- Is there a basic understanding of meeting rules?
- Who presents the backlog/requirements?
- Are open questions discussed immediately, or is time given for reflection?
- How is the effort/complexity estimated? Is a method (e.g., Planning Poker) used?
- Who is allowed to participate in the estimation?
- Who determines the sprint scope?
- Are there regulations for requirements (Definition of Done, etc.)?
- Who creates the work items?
- Who documents the work items?
- Are stakeholders allowed to participate in the meeting?
- How are acceptance (go/no go) decisions documented?

